

BELLY OF THE BEAST: INSIGHTS FROM DEVELOPING A VR INTERACTIVE MUSIC EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the design process for key interaction components in *Belly of the Beast*, a VR interactive music experience. In the experience, users manipulate a dynamic spatial musical composition in real-time within a room-scale immersive environment. The experience attempts to reimagine the role of the audience in music through active participation afforded by interactive technologies. This research documents key creative and technical developments in the form of a practice-based case study, leading to the design of a series of interactive musical interfaces presented in the final demo project. Insights into the functionality of these interfaces are provided through audience observations during the XR showcase at SXSW Sydney 2024, where the project was exhibited. The findings present future design considerations for VR interactive music experiences, notably in the importance of intuitive user interfaces, clear interaction design, and a careful balance between guided exploration and creative freedom. This work underscores VR's potential to transform audio composition and interaction, offering novel possibilities for creative expression in this emerging medium.

1. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

When you mention Virtual Reality (VR) music to most people, the first thing they'll likely think of is *Beat Saber*. And for good reason, music and rhythm games dominate popular perceptions of VR music experiences. *Beat Saber*, for example, is among the highest-rated VR apps on Steam, with a 96% positive review score as per a VR market analysis conducted in [1]. More broadly, music and rhythm were found to be the highest-rated genre in VR applications [2]. However, at its core, *Beat Saber* is a rhythm game first and a music experience second. Players follow predetermined patterns, slicing notes in time rather than shaping the music itself. The potential for VR to offer new and accessible ways for audiences to actively engage with popular music is only beginning to be explored [3].

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Unlike traditional listening environments, VR enables real-time interaction within a Virtual Environment (VE), allowing users to participate in music dynamically rather than passively. This shift redefines the role of the listener, transforming them from an observer into an active creator. These participatory music experiences challenge conventional listening paradigms by inviting audiences to interact with the composition as it unfolds. Small's [4] philosophy of musicking, which views music as a participatory, relational activity rather than a fixed object, appears to be particularly applicable to VR interactive music experiences.

As immersive technologies move into mainstream media, it is timely to explore how these experiences can extend beyond experimental contexts and into broader, more accessible applications. This reflects a shift towards the 'creator economy' and the 'consumer-creator' that has been observed in the music industry by Mulligan [5], who comments, "Not only will casual music creation become mainstream, it will trigger an unprecedented widening of the music creator economy funnel." While VR has been leveraged for music games, composition, and spatial mixing (see examples in [6]), relatively few applications place the user at the intersection of audience member and musical creator. This audience participation requires shifting the experience from passive reception to active co-creation [7].

This paper examines the development of *Belly of the Beast*, an interactive VR music experience designed to explore the intersection of immersive audio and audience participation. By describing the novel interaction paradigms used in the final demo, key design decisions made throughout an iterative development process, as well as observations of audience interactions with the work at SXSW Sydney 2024, this research serves as a case study in how VR can transfer creative agency from composer to audience, allowing users to sculpt and perform music within a 3D virtual space.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS

2.1 Interactive Music Considerations in XR

Research on interactive music in Extended Reality (XR) has been increasing in recent years, as can be observed through a comprehensive overview in [8]. Studies in interactive music suggest that spatial audio playback and real-time control over musical parameters can enhance both im-

mersion and user agency [9]. Furthermore, systems that allow users to manipulate sound objects within a 3D environment offer new possibilities for participatory composition, bridging the gap between performer and listener [10].

Research into interface modules for XR music has further highlighted that enabling users to physically interact with sound, through gestures, movement, or object manipulation, can deepen their connection to the music [11]. Berthaut [12] found that existing 3D interaction techniques offer significant opportunities for musical expression through immersive virtual musical instruments, but they require adaptation to better support expressive musical interaction, including improved selection and manipulation of multiple objects, hybrid interaction techniques, and enhanced visual feedback for users.

The design of interactive music systems in VR must consider usability, accessibility, and engagement. These factors contribute to the immersive experience, which is a key design goal in VEs [13]. In a systematic review of audio's impact on immersive experience in XR and digital games, Hedges et al. [14] showed that a number of studies utilizing interactive music techniques in VEs had a positive impact on the immersive experience. Furthermore, design guidelines for artful VR design presented in [15] require balancing doing (interaction and goal-driven action) with being (presence and reflection). Further guidelines include leveraging the unique affordances of VR rather than porting existing interactions, designing for immersion, supporting embodiment and multimodal interaction, and fostering play and social engagement, particularly in musical VR experiences.

While not specifically set in XR, a study by Wu and Bryan-Kinns [16] investigated factors affecting non-musicians' creative engagement with a tangible interactive musical system, offering relevant insights. They found that an experiential exploratory goal (aiming for a hedonic experience) encourages users' creative engagement more than a utilitarian creative goal (aiming for a concrete output) [16]. Their results also indicated that supporting users in replaying their musical ideas increased some aspects of creative engagement, which was further enhanced when they were able to edit their creations. Additionally, creative engagement increased when the interface supported users in planning ahead [16]. This research highlights the importance of motivational orientation and specific interface features in fostering non-musicians' creative involvement.

While these provide an array of approaches, research suggests that excessive complexity can deter engagement, particularly among users with limited musical experience [17]. A primary challenge is developing intuitive interaction methods that encourage participation without overwhelming the user. The impact on cognitive load is a crucial factor to VR user enjoyment, and prior research has shown that minimizing hardware obstruction, such as using hand-tracking instead of VR controllers, is preferred for direct touch interactions [18].

2.2 VR Interactive Music Experiences

While this work focuses on interactive music, it is important to note that VR has also been leveraged to create many non-interactive listening experiences, such as virtual string quartet performances that prioritize acoustic and visual fidelity [19, 20] and high-order Ambisonic opera recordings [21]. These continue to provide interesting ways for audiences to experience music passively using VR. However, the current landscape of interactive VR music experiences is rapidly evolving, offering new ways to engage with music beyond traditional listening and performance models. While the number of commercially available VR music applications remains relatively small compared to other gaming and entertainment experiences, there is a growing movement toward immersive and participatory musical environments.

In their review of immersive VR music experiences, Loveridge [6] examines various categories, from music creation tools like *Virtuoso* and *Electronauts*, which enable virtual instrument play, to rhythm games such as *Beat Saber* and *Smash Drums*, combining challenge-based synchronized movement with music. VR also enhances music video experiences, with projects like *Pearl* and *Together EP* offering visually immersive storytelling. Performance training applications like *Stage Presence* and *Maestro VR* simulate live concerts and conducting, while social platforms such as *VRChat* enable networked music collaboration [8]. For instance, one case study evaluated a four-piece rock band performing together in a networked XR simulation of the renowned BBC Maida Vale Recording Studios [22]. Despite these innovations, Loveridge [6] observes that challenges remain, including latency in online performances, limited avatar expressiveness, and accessibility barriers due to hardware constraints.

A notable example of unique music interaction is *Tonandi* by Sigur Rós, developed for Magic Leap. This experience merges generative soundscapes with augmented reality (AR), allowing users to interact with a dynamically evolving musical environment. Unlike passive music consumption, *Tonandi* turns the act of listening into a tactile and exploratory process, where users can manipulate elements of the sound world through physical gestures utilizing hand-tracking. Similarly, *PatchWorld XR* extends the possibilities of musical interaction by providing a VE where users can compose, manipulate, and experience music in real time. Unlike conventional DAW-based music creation, *PatchWorld XR* enables intuitive and immersive composition through VR-native instruments and interactive spatial interfaces. This approach echoes the movement toward accessible and participatory music-making, where the technical barriers to music production are reduced, allowing anyone to engage with sound creatively.

A recent research field called the *Musical Metaverse*, presented in [23], explores a new frontier for networked music performance and social musical interactions in immersive environments. Unlike traditional VR music applications, the *Musical Metaverse* emphasizes multi-user collaboration, enabling musicians to perform together across distances using real-time, low-latency audio streaming. Boem

Figure 1: A panoramic view illustrating the main interactive components within the *Belly of the Beast* user experience. From left to right, the user can manipulate the Granular Synthesizer, rearrange the composition with the Grid Mixer, perform melodies on the Virtual Keyboard, and control the spatial mix via the Sound Spheres and Virtual Head.

et al. [24] analyzed interviews with experts on the topic of the *Musical Metaverse*, highlighting the need for better infrastructure, monetization strategies, and audience engagement tools to make it viable for broader adoption in music creation and live performance.

3. BELLY OF THE BEAST

Belly of the Beast is a VR interactive music experience developed for the Meta Quest 3 with headphones, built using the Unity game engine and Wwise, a powerful middleware for implementing interactive audio in real-time applications. By leveraging the hand-tracking and head-tracking capabilities of the VR headset, users can navigate a $4m \times 4m$ room-scale immersive VE where they interact with a progressive rock music composition. The core project team consisted of Jacob Hedges (first author - Audio Developer and Composer), Daniel Garrett (Creative Developer and Programmer), and Jaxon Sharp (Composer and Lyricist), with additional animation by Brandon Doray.

A key design decision was to provide minimal instructions within the experience, encouraging playful exploration and minimizing gamification, as music does not traditionally require a tutorial. Throughout the 5–10 minute experience, users manipulate the spatial audio mix, adjust the arrangement of instrumental parts, and play bespoke virtual instruments with their hands alongside the composition. These interactive components, illustrated visually in Figure 1 and technically in Figure 2, function in real time through custom VR user interfaces. This section details these components, focusing on their design process and the underlying interactive audio techniques. A video playthrough of the full experience can be viewed here ¹.

3.1 Core Interactive Audio Techniques

The interactivity in *Belly of the Beast* relies on established techniques common in game audio, facilitated by the inter-

play between the game engine (Unity) and the audio middleware (Wwise). Key among these are:

- **Real-Time Parameter Control (RTPC):** This allows data from the game engine, such as user hand position, object location, or other in-game events, to dynamically control various audio parameters in the audio middleware in real-time. This enables continuous and expressive modulation of sound characteristics like pitch, volume, filters, or effect levels based on user actions.
- **Dynamic Music Systems:** These systems enable the music to react to gameplay or user choices by switching between different pre-composed musical segments, layers, or variations. In Wwise, this is often achieved using "Music Switch Containers," which can transition between audio loops or segments based on game state variables or specific triggers, allowing for a non-linear and adaptive musical score.

The following descriptions of the interactive components will refer to these general concepts.

3.2 Developing the Interactive Components

The primary interactive components were developed as practice-based research through an iterative process, with their functionality and design refined based on testing and creative goals. Figure 2 provides a schematic overview of the data flow for each of the four main interactive components, from user input detected in Unity to audio processing and rendering managed by Wwise and the Meta XR Audio plugin, which renders audio objects using Meta's proprietary head-related transfer function (HRTF). The following subsections detail the design and functionality of each component, referencing this underlying architecture.

3.2.1 Sound Spheres and Virtual Head

The Sound Spheres act as user-movable sound emitters for individual instrument stems, allowing participants to create

¹ Video Link: <http://bit.ly/4bqx90T>

Figure 2: Technical diagram illustrating the signal flow and audio processing pipelines for the four primary interactive components. The numbered steps detail the data flow from user interaction in Unity, through real-time parameter control (RTPC) in Wwise, to the final binaural audio output.

their own spatial mix. The Virtual Head functions similarly for vocals, featuring a motion-captured animated face. The design process for these elements aimed to provide an intuitive and playful method for users to control the spatial mix. An early iteration involved mimicking a static 7.0.4 surround sound setup with invisible speaker objects in the VE, each playing a discrete stem rendered from Pro Tools. However, testing revealed that without visual references, users struggled to perceive the spatial characteristics of the mix. A subsequent version introduced five visible spheres for key instrumental stems (Bass, Synth, Guitar1, Guitar2, Vocals), which panned around the user on automated paths, while the drum mix was presented as a second-order Ambisonics field that responded to head rotation. While more aurally pleasing, this iteration still lacked direct user agency. This led to the current design of directly manipulable Sound Spheres, where Unity communicates the position of each sphere to Wwise for real-time spatialization by the Meta XR Audio plugin. To address initial difficulties in identifying which sphere corresponded to which instrument, visual cues like flashing based on audio levels and floating text labels were added. The Virtual Head further enhanced immersion for the vocal stem by applying motion capture animation from a vocal performance to a 3D head model.

3.2.2 Virtual Keyboard

The Virtual Keyboard offers a familiar interface for active musical participation. Interaction triggers a synthesizer tone with synchronized visual feedback, with keys mapped to the D Dorian scale, ensuring all notes are consistent with the underlying composition. Developed to enable easy musical co-creation, its design began as a basic 2D plane. A C# script was implemented to send XY coordinates of the

user's hand collision to Wwise, which used these values (via RTPCs) to trigger notes mapped to the scale from a synth plugin (SynthOne). Initial user testing focused on refining the synthesizer tone and determining an optimal number of keys for usability. Following this, the 2D plane was refined into the current 3D object with discrete, visually responsive keys to enhance affordance and feedback.

3.2.3 Granular Synthesizer

This unique 3D musical interface allows users to trigger and manipulate a granular synthesizer by moving their hand through a grid of cubes. The X, Y, and Z axes of hand movement are mapped to control pitch, granular position/tremolo speed, and low-pass filter frequency respectively. As the first interactive musical component developed, the goal was to leverage the 3D nature of VR for musical interaction. The design started with a 3D grid in Unity and a C# script to send the XYZ coordinates of the user's hand position to Wwise. These values, via RTPC, modulated a granular synthesis plugin (Soundseed Grain) processing a pre-recorded synthesizer sample from the main composition to ensure timbral consistency. Visual feedback, where cubes within the grid expand upon interaction, was added to reinforce the user's connection to the sound manipulation.

3.2.4 Grid Mixer

The Grid Mixer allows users to rearrange the composition by interacting with an array of cubes, providing dynamic arrangement capabilities. Each of the five columns represents an instrument, and the four rows select different 16-bar loops or a mute function. A key design choice was to keep the vocals stem linear, acting as a narrative anchor to

guide the overall composition. This interface was the final addition, stemming from a suggestion by the creative developer to give users more structural control over the music. As the composer, the first author was initially hesitant to relinquish control over the carefully crafted arrangement. However, initial testing immediately highlighted the significant creative potential of this feature. The design adapted the Virtual Keyboard's interaction model, where XY hand position data sent from Unity to Wwise controls a dynamic music system (specifically, a Wwise Music Switch Container). This system switches between different instrumental loops (or a mute state) for each track based on where the user's hand interacts with the grid. Visual feedback was implemented for the selected grid section, showing a green cube for a selection containing an active music loop, and a red cube for the mute function.

3.3 Overview of the Full VR Experience

Users begin the experience after a short briefing on the main interactions and the importance of exploring and touching as much as they can throughout the duration of the experience. Once they place on the headset, they are transported into a dark space with an ominous, droning soundscape. Tiny particles float around to provide a sense of space, and a green light emits from a small circular platform directly beneath their starting position within the VE. This platform represents the 'play area' of the experience. To the left is the Granular Synthesizer, and to their right is the Virtual Keyboard. Users can interact with these elements to explore their functionality and musical expressions before the main composition starts.

After a few seconds, a small white glowing orb emerges from the darkness and approaches the user, accompanied by a sound design cue, eventually landing within the play area. The orb emits a Geiger counter sound effect; as the user's hand moves closer, its size and the sound's intensity increase, prompting interaction. When the user's hand gets close enough, it triggers a loud explosion filling the space with white light. As this light gradually dissipates, the Sound Spheres and the Virtual Head float down around the user, and the Grid Mixer interface appears in front of them. During this transition, the composition begins with the 'Guitar 1' Sound Sphere playing the opening riff. Users can now interact with the Grid Mixer to turn on instruments and rearrange the composition as they please. They can also adjust the position of the Sound Spheres and Virtual Head to modify the spatial mix. After some time, the Virtual Head begins to sing, its face reacting to the motion capture animation of the vocal performance.

As the composition unfolds, flashes of light synchronized to the beat illuminate the space. An observant user will notice these flashes revealing an enormous human-like silhouette in the distance, with white glowing eyes that slowly blink. This main section lasts approximately four minutes, with vocals gradually building in intensity. A transition then occurs where the composition shifts to a distorted, sustained guitar chord growing into loud feedback. During this, the large human figure approaches and leans over the user, its features gradually revealed by the

Figure 3: Booth setup for *Belly of the Beast* at the XR showcase for SXSW Sydney 2024.

platform light. As the guitar feedback intensifies, the figure slowly opens its massive mouth, leading to a sudden rapid drum fill as it lunges forward and swallows the user whole, revealing itself as the 'Beast'.

Immediately following this mild jump scare, the Beast disappears, and a nuclear explosion erupts in the distance while the composition transitions into a heavy and intense piece, marking the conclusion of the current VR demo.

4. AUDIENCE OBSERVATIONS

The final demo version of *Belly of the Beast* was presented at the XR showcase for SXSW Sydney 2024. The showcase ran for five full days from 10:00 AM to 5:00 PM, taking place within a small section of the Tech and Innovation Expo stream of the festival, occurring inside a large exhibition hall. The XR showcase consisted of approximately 15 booths where exhibitors presented their XR works to festival attendees. The booth for *Belly of the Beast* accommodated one user at a time, as seen in Figure 3. Approximately 10–20 people demoed the experience each day, resulting in at least 50 individuals experiencing the full demo. For each user, the demo was presented as detailed in the previous section, including a brief introduction to the experience before commencing. After the demo ended, users were given space to react naturally, followed by a brief conversation about their experience.

Observations were documented at the end of each day using diary-style voice recordings, where the exhibitor (first author) described key audience feedback and reactions. This practice-based case study approach was intentionally chosen to evaluate the work within the real-world context of a public exhibition. The goal was not a formal, hypothesis-driven experiment, but rather to document the design process and gather qualitative insights from authentic user interactions. The value of this methodology lies in capturing immediate, in-the-wild feedback to inform the project's iterative design, providing insights that are difficult to obtain in a controlled laboratory setting. The key themes, findings, and design implications that emerged from these observations are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Audience Observations and Design Implications

Theme	Key Finding	Supporting Feedback (Quotes)	Design Implication
Usability & Onboarding	Users occasionally struggled to grasp interface functions (such as the Grid Mixer) without clear, in-world guidance and often forgot verbal pre-briefings.	<p>“...kept confusing it with volume control and didn’t understand that different loops were playing...”</p> <p>“...biggest feedback would be to make sure it’s obvious that the ball is spatializing a stem.”</p>	Introduce subtle, contextual visual or auditory prompts. Gradually introduce interactive elements to avoid overwhelming the user.
Interaction Mechanics	Users’ intuitive desire to “grab” objects conflicted with the designed open-palm mechanic. Critical interfaces were sometimes not immediately visible.	<p>“Everyone wants to grab and move the spheres and the face... they just want better mechanics for it.”</p> <p>“if they think something’s supposed to be happening and it’s not, it’s probably because they haven’t turned the sound on yet”</p>	Refine mechanics to better match user expectations (e.g., implement pinch-to-grab). Ensure key UI elements are prominent and accessible.
Playstyles & Narrative	A wide diversity in user playstyles (cautious vs. experimental) was observed. Key narrative elements were often missed.	<p>“It was funny seeing some people stack the balls in one spot, while others hit them away...”</p> <p>“Maybe 10% of people realized the beast was going to swallow them at the end... it wasn’t obvious enough.”</p>	Design for varied interaction styles. Enhance visual and auditory cues to ensure critical narrative moments are effectively communicated.
Music Interaction & Personalization	Musicians and non-musicians engaged differently. There was a strong desire for deeper control and content personalization.	<p>“The musical people really wanted polyphony; they wanted to use both hands and stack chords.”</p> <p>“Non-musicians played the instruments less out of not wanting to ‘break’ the experience.”</p> <p>“People showed interest in putting in their own or favorite artists’ songs.”</p>	Provide scalable interaction with simplified/advanced modes. Explore features for user-content integration (e.g., importing stems).

Taken together, these findings highlight a central theme: the need for a thoughtful balance between guided discovery and creative freedom. While users were enthusiastic about the novel forms of musical control, the observations consistently pointed toward the importance of intuitive mechanics, clear visual feedback, and scalable interfaces that can accommodate a wide range of user intentions and musical experience levels. These insights directly inform both the ongoing development of the project and the key design recommendations discussed in the following section.

5. DISCUSSION

This discussion synthesizes insights from the *Belly of the Beast* development process and audience observations into key design recommendations for VR interactive music experiences. By comparing design choices with user reactions, we identify ways to enhance engagement, usability, and musical interaction. These recommendations build on

prior design guidelines in VR music interaction to ensure alignment with broader principles.

5.1 Designing for Progressive Discovery

Our observations from SXSW Sydney strongly reinforce the need for progressive discovery in VR music experiences. While some users appreciated the lack of explicit instructions, others struggled to grasp the functions of key interfaces like the Grid Mixer and Sound Spheres. This aligns with Atherton and Wang’s [15] principle of balancing doing (active interaction) with being (presence and reflection), which is consistent with findings from Wu and Bryan-Kinns’ [16] showing that experiential exploratory goals encourage creative engagement. The verbal pre-demo explanations were often forgotten once users entered VR, reinforcing research that suggests in-world, context-sensitive onboarding is more effective. This aligns with Cavdir’s [25] findings, where step-by-step learning in a VR

music setting helped participants gradually discover gestural affordances while also encouraging them to explore possibilities they might otherwise overlook.

Future VR music experiences should introduce mechanics gradually through subtle visual or auditory prompts that fade as familiarity increases, ensuring usability without disrupting immersion. By refining onboarding to blend with the environment, the experience can better support access, making musical engagement more intuitive and inclusive for all users.

5.2 Leveraging Embodied Interaction

A significant insight from our audience observations was the clear disconnect between our designed interaction mechanics and users' intuitive expectations regarding embodied interaction. Many users instinctively attempted to grab and manipulate the Sound Spheres and Virtual Head, despite the system requiring a cupping gesture. Berthaut [12] highlights that VR musical interfaces must align with embodied intuition while supporting fine musical control. While early prototypes in the design process experimented with indirect spatialization methods (e.g., automated speaker paths), iterative testing revealed that direct manipulation fostered stronger engagement.

Atherton and Wang's [15] emphasis on total systems underscores the importance of multisensory integration in VR. The audience's preference for grab-and-move functionality supports a shift towards direct manipulation paradigms, which align with familiar VR interaction models and enhance immersion by reinforcing a coherent world. This is consistent with the idea that intuitive interaction, including clear visual feedback and physical affordances, is key for non-musicians to engage with novel musical interfaces [16]. By designing for well-embodied interaction, the experience encourages intentionality in virtual space.

5.3 Balancing Creative Freedom with Accessibility

Our findings revealed distinct interaction styles between musicians and non-musicians, underscoring the challenge of balancing creative freedom with broad accessibility. Musicians sought greater control, evident in their desire for polyphony in the Virtual Keyboard, whereas non-musicians hesitated, often fearing they would disrupt the composition. This reflects both Wu and Bryan-Kinns' [16] and Berthaut and Hachet's [10] findings that participatory music systems should cater to both exploratory and structured interaction styles. The challenge is to provide scalable interaction layers, ensuring that casual users can engage easily while allowing experienced musicians to access deeper functionality.

Atherton and Wang's [15] principle of access is central here, as making VR music accessible means designing interfaces that accommodate a range of skill levels. This concept also extends to personalization, which emerged as a strong user interest. Some participants envisioned integrating their own musical content into the system, echoing industry trends toward casual consumer music creation [5]. Future VR music platforms should explore customization

options, such as importing personal audio stems or adjusting instrument behavior, to broaden engagement and appeal. Furthermore, alternative approaches to utilizing 6DoF space should be explored, such as positioning different elements or versions of a composition across a much larger virtual world so that mixing can be controlled by navigating the world as well as by manipulating sound objects, as seen in [26, 27]. By championing expressive, participatory music-making, these experiences can further enhance creativity and social connection within VR environments.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study examined the iterative design and interaction paradigms of *Belly of the Beast*, a VR interactive music experience. Through a practice-based case study, utilizing audience observations at SXSW Sydney 2024, we gained rich qualitative insights into the creative potential and challenges of developing novel interactive music experiences in VR. Key findings underscored the importance of intuitive guidance and progressive discovery, the need for embodied interaction aligned with user expectations, and the value of balancing creative freedom with accessibility through scalable interaction layers. Additionally, audience responses suggest opportunities for personalized content integration, such as allowing users to import their own music or adapt musical parameters.

These insights have directly informed ongoing refinements to the *Belly of the Beast* experience. Building upon this foundational work, a future study is planned to conduct a more detailed experimental investigation, comparing user experiences between diverse audience groups within a revised *Belly of the Beast* environment. This upcoming research aims to further explore how design choices impact engagement and creative agency for users with varying levels of musical expertise.

Belly of the Beast demonstrates that VR music environments are more than just interactive sound spaces; they are performative ecosystems where users dynamically shape musical and spatial narratives. The varied playstyles observed reinforce that different users bring unique creative instincts to this medium. This research, as a practice-based case study, demonstrates the value of in-the-wild evaluations for informing the design of future VR music experiences that empower users as co-creators rather than passive listeners. As VR technology continues to evolve, there is an opportunity to further bridge the gap between audience participation and professional music creation.

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